

THE SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL NECESSITY OF IMPROVING THE SUGGESTIVE ABILITIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCE

¹Abdullayeva O.S., ²Shermatova M.I.

¹DSc, professor, Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute

²Teacher at the department "Pedagogy and Psychology" of the higher educational institution
"University of Business and Science"

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Abstract. *Since the acceleration of development and globalization in the fields of science, technology, and culture require a competency-based approach to teaching, suggestive competence is of particular scientific and scientific-methodological importance in forming, developing and improving the professional competence of future specialists at all stages of education, especially in higher education. Due to the current stage of the development of society, the change and modernization of the previous social structures is characterized by an increase in socio-psychological tension inherent in adults, children and school as a social institution. A modern teacher needs competences to influence child's personality at a professional level during the educational process and brings him to the first place. Currently, the development of suggestive competence and its various aspects, among other types of competence, has become one of the urgent tasks at all levels of education.*

Keywords: *improvement, suggestive competence, training process, teacher, professional activity, higher educational institution.*

INTRODUCTION

In the theory of world pedagogical education, suggestive competence in raising competent and competitive personnel in line with international standards, in particular, organizational and pedagogical processes of improving suggestive competence in future teachers, improving suggestive competence, theoretical knowledge about suggestibility, awareness of suggestive actions, the quality of performed suggestive actions, the ability to demonstrate suggestive competence in a new situation and explain it to others have been proven to be of significant scientific, theoretical and practical importance. In world scientific research institutions and higher education institutions considerable research is also being done to develop competence knowledge of future specialists, to learn professional knowledge, qualifications and skills, suggestiveness related to specialty and to effectively establish activities to apply it in professional activities. In the concept of education until 2030 adopted by international organizations and developed countries, "Creating an opportunity to receive quality education throughout life" was defined as an important task. This is one of the important factors that indicate the directions of scientific research in the field of professional competence development of future pedagogues-specialists. The development and improvement of suggestive competence of students studying in pedagogical education directions is the intellectual basis of forming professional competences in them, and it is necessary to conduct research in these directions.

In recent years, serious reforms of the education system in our country have been implemented to raise the quality and efficiency of education, as well as to enhance the professional

competence of future specialists, including teachers of science of pedagogy. The main task is to introduce modern methods for improving suggestive competence among future pedagogy teachers. The essence of today's education policy is to "develop our young people who think independently, possess high intellectual and spiritual potential to become individuals who do not fall behind their peers in any field on a global scale". Teaching the science of pedagogy aims to increase the effectiveness of education by creating a new, modern methodology. Among other things, there is a task of training professors and teachers in higher educational institutions who love and value their field, and who possess deep knowledge, skills, and professional abilities. This highlights the relevance of studying issues related to the improvement and development of suggestive competence, which is the foundation of professional competence for future teachers of pedagogy.

METHODOLOGY

A number of foreign scientists (I.P. Pavlov, I.M. Sechenov, V.M. Bekhterev, A.F. Lazursky, S.L. Rubinshtein, A.A. Bodalev, K.I. Platonov, V.N. Myasishchev, A.M. Svyadosch) developed concepts of the mechanism of suggestibility. Suggestive activity is recognized as a factor of human interaction in the process of communication (V.A. Bakeev, A.G. Kovalev, V.N. Kulikov, A.V. Petrovsky, K.K. Platonov, B.F. Porshnev, etc.). Works analyzing the role of suggestibility in the pedagogical process (Guyo, V.M. Bekhterev, P.P. Blonsky, S.V. Kravkov, A.S. Makarenko) are important. It is worth noting here that in solving a number of issues related to self-hypnosis in the system of self-education of schoolchildren (I.E. Schwartz, L.V. Gasheva, A.S. Novoselova, B.K. Moiseev, Z.A. Cherepanova, etc.), several recommendations have been developed. The mentioned studies will help to form suggestive skills in terms of modern scientific achievements and, at the same time, to improve taking into account its history and theory.

Taking into account that one of the goals of the research is to observe the development of student's personality, the problems of using influence in the history and theory of pedagogy were considered. In this process, attention is mainly focused on the following aspects:

1. Historical-pedagogical description of the problem;
2. Analysis of learning to use influence in the pedagogical process in current conditions;
3. Analysis of the concepts of "Impact", "Be affected".

A number of rules are listed related to the theory of suggestibility: 1) the importance of the authority to exercise influence; 2) influencing communication with confidence; 3) the need to accept and share ideas that should be instilled in others; 4) the dependence of the power of influence on the tone of voice, which is enhanced by facial expressions. Educators should show more respect for human nature, and try not to suppress and develop the inner feelings of their students, to consciously and confidently influence the educational process, to educate students within the framework of moral standards.

By considering the essence of suggestibility as a phenomenon based on influencing abilities, a list of necessary knowledge was determined:

1. Knowledge as a method of influencing education and its place in the system of methods; knowledge about the specific features of influencing, its goals and tasks, the operative composition of influencing skills.

2. Knowledge in the field of influence theory: the mechanism of influence; classification of types of influence and possibilities of using them in pedagogy; characteristics of the counter-influence process and its importance for the pedagogical process;

3. Knowledge of the ability to influence as a component of the personality structure; to determine the level of influence in the organization of the educational process and to know the methods of taking the latter into account;

4. Knowledge of the impact of technology and the conditions for its effective implementation.

Explaining the totality of a teacher's professional intellectual and practical actions through suggestive skills helps form students' views and attitudes toward the world around them and activates the processes of self-management and self-education. It is explained that this approach allows for the use of influence, thereby enabling the possibility of changing and correcting various aspects of a student's mind and behavior. The author's definition is as follows: "Suggestive skills in teachers are designed to evoke positive emotional states in students. The indicator of these skills is teacher's speech, which penetrates into the spiritual and moral essence of students' activities and relationships. The influence exerted during interaction is derived from other professional and pedagogical skills". Skills such as organizational, communicative, perceptive, and gnostic have an integral effect on the developing personality of the student due to their inextricable connection with one another.

REALIZATION OF THE CONCEPT

The following suggestive processes, which are considered important in the development of teacher's personality, are presented:

1. Hypnosis: Using hypnotic techniques to create deep relaxation and alter the mind of the student. It helps the teacher to create a positive attitude and motivate the student to achieve the goals.

2. Positive Programming: Using positive statements and affirmations to reinforce student's positive thoughts and beliefs. This helps the teacher to create a positive atmosphere and increase student's self-esteem.

3. Metaphors: using figurative expressions and stories to convey certain lessons or meanings. Metaphors are an effective way of influencing reader's subconscious, helping them to better understand and remember the material.

4. Positive Modeling: Demonstrating desired behaviors and attitudes by the teacher to inspire students to imitate. Teachers can be role models for their students and help develop positive skills and values.

5. Demonstrating: Using mental images and visuals to help students achieve their goals and increase their motivation. Teachers can use visual exercises to help students visualize themselves as successful people.

During the moment "Using suggestive methods" in the lecture classes, the students are explained about the suggestive methods related to the new topic. After analyzing the situation, it was found that students' existing knowledge of suggestive methods will be strengthened on the basis of repetition, enriched with new knowledge, and it will ensure the easy and perfect mastery of new topic of the lecture by the students.

More precisely, the moment "Using suggestive methods" held at the beginning of the lecture prepares students to study the topic, serves to develop their suggestive competence. After the teacher presents the topic and its plan, he conducts the moment "Using suggestive methods". In this process, basic words and phrases related to the topic, that is, methods, are referred to the students. The moment "Using suggestive methods" can be carried out in an integrative state with

methods of "Brainstorming", "Problem situation", "Cluster", "Stair-step", "Working in small groups".

In practical and seminar sessions, the moment "Using suggestive methods" allows to strengthen the scientific-theoretical knowledge obtained in the lecture, prove, substantiate, explain, and analyze in practical terms. In the "interpreting method", the theoretical information learned by the student, suggestive methods related to science are widely used in practice, it prepares the ground for the development of the ability of creating an atmosphere of trust and respect in students, and the application of the knowledge gained in their specialty in their work.

In addition to teaching pedagogic subjects, in order to improve the suggestive competence of students, it is effective to organize the free time of students in a proper and meaningful way, to develop their love for science, and to organize the circle "Young Suggestor". 15-20 talented students of different courses and groups who are interested in science are accepted as members of the club. It is recommended to conduct circle training twice a month on specific days of the second and fourth weeks. Each lesson is important in improving the suggestive competence of students: lectures, practical and seminar classes, as well as independent education, current, intermediate, final control and group classes. It will be effective only if it covers all teaching processes.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

A set of mental and practical actions of a teacher, including professional qualities, influences teacher's self-education, as well as various aspects of students' behavior, consciousness, views, and attitudes. Suggestiveness allows for the activation of self-control processes.

The group of suggestive skills is a necessary element in teacher's professional activity. Suggestive skills are based on affect - an objectively present factor in human interaction. In the educational process, suggestiveness is used as a method of pedagogical influence, the main purpose of which is to stimulate the self-development mechanisms of student's personality.

Considering suggestive abilities from the point of view of a systematic approach, it is possible to identify the main structural elements of this phenomenon, which represent a sequence of actions united by a single goal.

The main elements of suggestiveness: collection and analysis of facts describing the real motives of student behavior; forming a positive attitude (mood) of the teacher to the student; establishing a trusting relationship with the teacher; determining the purpose of suggestive influence, personal development prospects; determining student's level of influence; analyzing the social environment and the results of its impact on the student; predicting a possible counteroffer; choosing a suggestive effect that matches student's characteristics and educational goals, and performing a direct suggestive act control the dynamics of student's personality development.

In each of the conditions of the main elements of suggestibility, depending on the general conditions, the teacher carries out the influence and performs its own special functions. Their implementation is ensured by a set of pedagogical skills.

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